

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF THREE MODES OF ASSIGNMENT PRACTICES IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

This project titled as A Study on Effectiveness of Three Modes of Assignment Practices in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur focuses on effective utilize the assignment practices among students. The sample size for this study is 220. The research design carried out for this study is descriptive types of research. Primary data are collected from the respondents of various department students through a structured undisguised questionnaire. Statistical tool like graphs, internal estimation, chi-squared test and correlation have been used for the purpose of analysis. The findings of the study were arrived based on analysis conducted. Some of the major findings of the study relate to increase necessity of having respondents by Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur and priority to have written and seminar assignments cover by majority of the respondents. The study have been concluded that the performance of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur is excellent in comparison with its another college and that the college has high growth prospects in future years to come.

Key Words: Assignment, Seminar, Power Point Presentation, Education

Introduction:

Academic writing is an important part of every curriculum whether you are in high school or you are a university student. The objective of all such assignments is to see how better you can express yourself through words and how much you know about a subject. In the introduction you present the assignment's research question and its background, so as to show why it will be interesting to find the answer.

An assignment is a task that someone is given to do, usually as part of their job. An assignment is also a piece of academic work given to students. The project assignment is a compulsory part of the course and should be carried out by student groups. The results of this assignment contribute 50% of the final course score. It will therefore, require considerable efforts in time, input as well as critical thinking from each student. It is required that the student group will work independently throughout the project work including: information searching, literature study, data treatment /analysis, material compiling and the final reporting.

Meaning:

The term assignment is quite familiar to the teacher as well as pupil. Usually any exercise given by the teacher to the pupil as part of the lesson, any follow up work suggested for study is called an assignment. The principle aim of any education is to teach the pupil to work on his own responsibility. An assignment is a task or piece of work that you re given to do, especially as part of your job or studies. The assessment for the course involves written assignments and practical tests. Transfer of ownership of a property, or of benefit, interest, liabilities, and rights under a contract by one party to another party by signing a document called deed assignment. An assignment is a task that someone is given to do, usually as part of their job. My first major assignment as a reporter was to cover a large riot. An assignment is also a piece of academic work given to students.

Definition:

An assignment in which the transfer is complete and leaves the assignor with no interest in the property or right transferred. Assignment is defined as a position held in government or an organization that bears great responsibility. Homework assignment is a set of tasks assigned to students by their teachers to be completed outside the class. Assignment usually takes the form off written pieces of work that are set by your course tutors. They also usually contribute towards your final course mark or grade. The most common written assignments that students are asked to produce are essays or reports.

Components of Elements:

- **Significant Content:** Significant content means you need some really meaty standards to address. you have to take a look at what big areas will be drawn in while you are learning. Don't kill yourself check-

marking every single ELA standard known to man. Remember, you want to be sure your student5s actually attained knowledge with some type of assessment.

- **A need to know:** How are you going to engage your students? The “need to know” generally has some kind of entry event to get students curiosity up and questions going. This could be a video, an interview, or a real-aloud. When I teach force and motion through designing a roller coaster, the entry event is watching point-of-view rides on some of the world’s most wild coasters. Other times, I bring in e mystery box with some unusual object inside. Anything to get kids’ minds racing and saying, “I need to know more!”
- **Driving Question:** There’s a lot of semantic discussion about the driving question vs. a philosophical question or an essential question. The important part is threat your students are going to answer through in depth inquiry. A good driving question will capture the projects focus, be easy to understand, and provide a sense of challenge. All the activities will combine to help provide an answer to this question. If you can look up the answer in one quick internet search, the question isn’t complex enough.
- **Student Voice and Choice:** Intrinsic motivation shines when students take responsibility and ownership over their own learning. Choice allows for projects to become personally meaningful and relevant to students. It also makes sense for teachers to gradually allow more voice and choice as their experience with PBL grows.
- **21st Century Skills:** This has been a buzz word for some time. How do schools develop more critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication? Filling in bubbles on standardized tests is not the solution. On the other hand, giving students the opportunity to do things like presenting a unique idea, creating tasks after a team brainstorm, or shifting through internet resources allows them to practices skills and builds experience.
- **Inquiry and Innovation:** Students like a good question just like the rest of us. Better yet, students love to answer questions they pose. Students are more than able to create new questions, test ideas, and interpret conclusions. In fact, students can learn from failure, if we said up the right environment. “With real inquiry comes real innovation.
- **Feedback and Revision:** Often times this step is neglected or rushed. High quality, impressive work is often the result of multiple iterations and authentic feedback. The teacher, along with peers, participates in a cycle of review and coaching, rather than consternation. Rounds of improvements stress the fact work should be of a certain standard. PBL also shows that learning is a process, rather than a race with a start and finish.
- **Authentic Audience, Publicly Presented Product:** I was once at a school where teachers joked that student work often went to the secret file folder. That folder shared a home with the Grouch, it was the trash. How do you think that made students feel? Schoolwork, just like any work, is more meaningful when other people benefit, or are inspired, by it. Introducing final projects to a public audience like parents, community leaders, professors, or they internet opens up a world of possibilities. Students are valued as leaners and individuals. Talk about high expectations!

Literature Review:

Hodges (1993) explored the theory that secondary students who are not proficient writers have difficulty because they lack intensive practice and experience in reading and writing, and because they lack vocabulary. Her experiment included teaching study skills, implementing a rigorous vocabulary program focusing on etymology, structure and self-discipline, providing instruction in speed reading, Teaching through thematic units, instructing students in the written conventions of Grammar, and integrating writing, speaking, and listening. At the end of the year, results of the standardized test showed students had made significant growth in their writing skills. Hodges’s study provided evidence that students benefit from direct instruction in the areas of vocabulary and the conventions of written language. This supports the use of guided instruction in these areas during the experimental phase of the study. students are defined as “at-risk” when they meet one or more of the following characteristics: unsatisfactory standardized test scores; failing grades in core academic subjects; victim of child abuse or neglect; pregnant teenager or teenage parent; eligible for fi-ee or reduced price lunch due to family poverty; family history of school failure, incarceration, or substance abuse; below grade level performance in English language and communication skills; or atypical behavior or attendance patterns. Forty-eight percent of Hesperia Middle School’s students are considered at-risk of academic failure. This information will provide evidence for the background of the study, and the definition of “at-risk” will be used in selecting the participants for the study. Anderson, Benjamin & Fuss, 1994; Arias & Walker, 2004; Borg & Shapiro, 1996; Greene, 1997; Jensen & Owen, 2001) in this paper, we examine the impact of graded homework on the test performance of students taking economics courses. Recently, researchers have done extensive amounts of work on how to improve performance of economics students.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study on Effectiveness of three modes of assignment practices in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

- To evaluate the student performance in the three modes of assignments.
- To study the effective utilization of three modes of assignment practices to the student.
- To study the using of these three modes of assignment practices to improve the internal marks.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. The methodology students for the study were mainly through primary data and secondary data.

Research Design:

A study was carried out with the descriptive type of research.

Sample Design:

Random sampling method is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

The sample size of the study is limited to 220.

Method of Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Data was collected with the help of structure questionnaires from 220 students of the college.

Tools used for Statistical Analysis:

The statistical tools used in this study are

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Research Hypothesis:

Chi-Squared Test for Independence:

A chi-squared test for independence is applied when you have two categorical variables from a single population. It is used to determine whether there is a significant association between the two variables. The best consists of four steps: (1) state the hypothesis, (2) formulate an analysis plan, (3) analyze sample data, and (4) interpret results. State the hypothesis. a chi-square test for independence is conducted on two categorical variables. Suppose that variable A has r levels, and variable B has c levels. The null hypothesis states that knowing the level Variable A does not help you predict the level of Variable B. that is the variables are independent. The alternative hypothesis states that the variables are not independent. Formulate analysis plan. The analysis plan describes how to use sample data to accept or reject the null hypothesis. The plan should specify a significance level and should identify the chi-squared test for independence as the test statistics.

The degree of freedom (DF) is equal to: $DF = (r-1) * (c-1)$

Where r is the number of levels for one categorical variable, and c is the number of levels for the other categorical variable. Expected frequencies the expected frequency counts are computed separately for each level of one categorical variable at each level of the other categorical variable. Compute r*c expected frequencies, according to the following formula.

$$E_{r,c} = (nr * nc) / n$$

where $E_{r,c}$ is the expected frequency count for level r of Variable A and level c of variable B, nr is the total number of sample observations at level r of Variable A, nc is the total number of sample observations at level c of Variable B, and n is the total sample size. Test statistic. The test statistic is a chi-square random variable (χ^2) defines by the following equation.

$$\chi^2 = \sum [(O_{r,c} - E_{r,c})^2 / E_{r,c}]$$

Where $O_{r,c}$ is the observed frequency count at level r of Variable A and level c of Variable B, and $E_{r,c}$ is the expected frequency count at level r of Variable A and level c of Variable B. P-value. The P-value is the probability of observing a sample statistic as extreme as the test statistic. Since the test statistic is a chi-square, use the Chi-square distribution Calculator to assess the probability associated with the test statistic. Use the degrees of freedom computed above. Interpret results. If the sample findings are unlikely, given the null hypothesis, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis. Typically, this involves comparing the P-value to the significance level, and rejecting the null hypothesis when the P-value is less than the significance level.

Findings:

- 57% of the respondents are their improve student's performance of assignment practices.
- 57% of respondents are agreeing to their opportunity express student's talent in the assignment practices.
- 50% of respondents are agreeing to their help to improve the self-confidence in the assignment practices.
- 37% of respondents are learning to understand their by assignment practices.
- 46% of respondents are agreeing to improve other skill such as paper presentation and conference in assignment practices.

- 55% of respondents are agreeing to the assignment practices improve the communication skill in the assignment practices.
- 50% of respondents are agree to their effective utilize the written assignment.
- 55% of respondents are agree to their effective utilize the seminar assignment.
- 48% of respondents are neutral to their effective utilize the PPT assignment.
- 49% of respondents are agree to their assignment practices are well planned.
- 39% of respondent are neutral to their assignment practices time schedule.
- 46% of respondents are agreeing to their assignment practices help to improve the internal marks in assignment practices.

Conclusion:

It is concluded from the perception of the sample respondents Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, a good number (80%) of respondents expressed positively or confident enough to balance their routine work smoothly/comfortably. Due to some lack of communication, stress and not the study concentrate some of the respondents (20%) expressed their inability to balance their work and it is also [proved that the significant level in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College high on some of the practices like studying hours, present hours of study, over time evening class. Hence it is concluded that Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College students are more agreeing with all the above practices than another college students. therefore it is suggested that the management of selected colleges to plan and take necessary steps to motivate them to their personality and performance by providing stress reducing activities like proving many task game, freedom. Overall assignment practices are good in written and seminar assignment. so students are improve the communication skill and writing skill.

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